

NAIL PSORIASIS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN DERMOSCOPIC AND CLINICAL NAPSI SCORING

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate and compare the effectiveness of dermoscopic Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (DNAPSI) with clinical Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI) in detecting early nail changes in patients with psoriasis.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study: Conducted at Dermatology department of Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, from January 2024 to December 2024.

Methodology: A total of 95 patients diagnosed with chronic plaque psoriasis were included. Each patient underwent detailed clinical examination, and NAPSI scores were calculated. Subsequently, dermoscopic evaluation of nails was performed, and DNAPSI scores were recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27.0. Mean scores were compared, and statistical significance was determined with a p -value ≤ 0.05 .

Results: Dermoscopic examination revealed additional subclinical nail features, including dilated capillaries, longitudinal erythema, and fuzzy lunula, which were not detectable on routine clinical examination. The mean DNAPSI score was significantly higher compared to the clinical NAPSI score ($p < 0.05$), indicating superior sensitivity of dermoscopy in identifying early and subtle nail changes associated with psoriasis.

Conclusion: Dermoscopy is a more sensitive and effective tool than conventional clinical examination for the assessment of nail psoriasis. Its integration into routine dermatological practice may facilitate early diagnosis, improve disease monitoring, and enhance overall patient management.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic, multi-systemic inflammatory disorder influenced by genetic and environmental factors, affecting the skin, nails, and other body systems [1, 2]. Nail psoriasis (NP) affects up to 50% of psoriatic patients [3] and is seen in 80-90% of arthropathic psoriasis cases [4], significantly impacting patients' quality of life by altering social and professional interactions [5]. NP involves multiple nail segments [6], and its clinical manifestations depend on the affected subunit [7-9]. It is classified into matrix involvement (type 1) and bed involvement (type 2), with common changes including pitting, oil drops, onycholysis, splinter haemorrhages, and subungual hyperkeratosis [6, 10]. Vascular alterations and angiogenesis, key features of psoriasis, are evident in nails and can precede visible skin lesions [1, 11]. The Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI) is a tool used to evaluate NP severity by scoring changes in the nail matrix and bed [4]. Dermoscopy, a non-invasive diagnostic tool [12], has revolutionised NP evaluation by enhancing visualisation of nail structures [13]. Features such as pitting, longitudinal erythema, dilated capillaries, salmon patches, and peripheral white halos are detected during clinical examinations. Dermoscopy, however, offers excellent insight into their study, which is difficult to determine with the naked eye [2, 14, 15]. Polarised and non-polarised dermoscopy modes enable the identification of both superficial and deep nail changes [15]. Studies highlight the utility of dermoscopy in detecting specific NP features and its potential to identify subclinical cases [2,16].

Objective

This study aims to explore the role of dermoscopy in the early detection and diagnosis of NP and to compare its effectiveness with traditional clinical scoring methods, such as NAPSI and dermoscopic NAPSI (DNAPSI). By identifying subtle, early nail changes during psoriasis progression, dermoscopy may offer a reliable and practical approach for prognosis and management, minimising the disease's physical and psychological impact.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional, observational study conducted to evaluate and compare clinical and dermoscopic assessment of nail psoriasis in patients with chronic plaque psoriasis. The study was carried out at the Department of Dermatology, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, a tertiary care center catering to a diverse patient population from January 2024 to December 2024. A total of 95 adult patients diagnosed with chronic plaque psoriasis were included in the study. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit patients presenting to the dermatology outpatient department who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Patients of both genders with a confirmed diagnosis of chronic plaque psoriasis and presenting with visible nail changes were included. Patients who were pregnant or had other nail disorders such as onychomycosis, lichen planus, alopecia areata, eczema, or exfoliative dermatosis were excluded. Additionally, patients who had already received effective treatment for nail psoriasis or other therapeutic modalities were not included to avoid confounding of results.

Data Collection

After obtaining ethical approval from the institutional review board, informed consent was taken from all participants. Demographic details including age, gender, and duration of disease were recorded. Each patient underwent a detailed clinical examination of fingernails, and findings were scored using the Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI). Subsequently, dermoscopic examination was performed using a HEINE DELTA 30 dermoscope attached to a Galaxy S22 Ultra camera to enhance visualization. Dermoscopic features such as dilated capillaries, longitudinal erythema, and fuzzy lunula were documented, and scores were recalculated using the dermoscopic Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (DNAPSI). All examinations were conducted under standardized conditions to ensure consistency.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. Quantitative variables such as age and NAPSI/DNAPSI scores were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while qualitative variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Paired t-test was applied to compare the mean NAPSI and DNAPSI scores. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between clinical and dermoscopic scores. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

total of 95 patients were included, with a male predominance of 53 (56%) compared to 42 (44%) females. The mean age of participants was 39.94 ± 14.04 years, with a wide range from 18 to 80 years, indicating inclusion of both young and elderly patients. The mean disease duration was 9.69 years, ranging from 1 to 40 years, reflecting considerable variability in chronicity of psoriasis among participants. The correlation between disease duration and NAPSI score was very weak ($r = 0.06$), suggesting that the severity of nail involvement does not significantly depend on the duration of the disease.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n = 95)

Variable	Category	Value
Gender	Male	53 (56%)
	Female	42 (44%)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	39.94 ± 14.04
	Range	18 - 80
Disease Duration (years)	Mean	9.69
	Range	1 - 40
Correlation (Disease Duration vs NAPSI)	r-value	0.06

Among nail bed findings, distal onycholysis was the most common feature on clinical examination (62, 35.03%), while dermoscopy identified splinter hemorrhages (59, 24.08%) and dilated hyponychial capillaries (63, 25.71%) more prominently. Notably, dilated hyponychial capillaries were rarely detected clinically (6, 3.39%) but were frequently observed on

dermoscopy, highlighting the enhanced sensitivity of DNAPSI in identifying vascular changes. Other features such as oil drop sign and subungual hyperkeratosis showed relatively comparable frequencies between both methods. Regarding nail matrix findings, pitting remained the most common feature in both NAPSI (67, 38.07%) and DNAPSI (68, 37.36%).

Table 2: Comparison of Nail Findings by NAPSI and DNAPSI

Variable	Feature	NAPSI n (%)	DNAPSI n (%)
Nail Bed Findings	Distal Onycholysis	62 (35.03%)	61 (24.9%)
	Splinter Hemorrhage	51 (28.81%)	59 (24.08%)
	Oil Drop Sign	33 (18.64%)	36 (14.69%)
	Subungual Hyperkeratosis	25 (14.12%)	26 (10.61%)
	Dilated Hyponychial Capillaries	6 (3.39%)	63 (25.71%)
Nail Matrix Findings	Pitting	67 (38.07%)	68 (37.36%)
	Leukonychia	22 (12.5%)	22 (12.09%)
	Longitudinal Grooves	21 (11.93%)	21 (11.54%)
	Transverse Grooves	20 (11.36%)	22 (12.09%)
	Trachyonychia	19 (10.8%)	19 (10.44%)
	Crumbling	14 (7.95%)	—

	Red Spots on Lunula	3 (1.7%)	3 (1.65%)
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The mean PASI score was 15.678 ± 9.1967 , indicating moderate severity of skin involvement among participants. The mean NAPSI score was 17.24 ± 11.448 , while the mean DNAPSI score

was higher at 20.76 ± 11.440 , with DNAPSI also showing a wider range of values (3-60) compared to NAPSI (1-54).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Severity Scores (n = 95)

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
PASI Score	95	2.6	40.0	15.678	9.1967
NAPSI	95	1	54	17.24	11.448
DNAPSI	95	3	60	20.76	11.440

A weak but statistically significant positive correlation was observed between PASI and NAPSİ scores ($r = 0.371$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that nail severity increases with skin disease severity to some extent, although the relationship is not strong. In contrast, a very strong positive

correlation was found between NAPSİ and DNAPSİ ($r = 0.953$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that both scoring systems measure similar aspects of disease severity, with DNAPSİ providing a more sensitive assessment.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation (r)	p-value
PASI vs NAPSİ	0.371	<0.001
NAPSİ vs DNAPSİ	0.953	<0.001
Disease Duration vs NAPSİ	0.06	–

Discussion

Dermoscopy, which transformed the treatment of pigmented skin lesions, has more recently become a reliable diagnostic method for a variety of infections and inflammatory dermatoses [23]. Its application in nail disorders has expanded rapidly, yet evidence regarding its diagnostic value in inflammatory nail disorders remains limited due to overlap with other nail conditions. Further, because nail psoriasis is strongly associated with psoriatic arthritis, early detection of nail changes is critical for long-term management [1]. This study demonstrates that dermoscopy is a rapid, reproducible and noninvasive adjunct that enhances diagnostic accuracy of NP compared with clinical exam alone. DNAPSİ scores were consistently higher than NAPSİ scores, perhaps due to dermoscopy’s enhanced ability to detect vascular changes, such as dilated capillaries and longitudinal erythema, which aligns with prior research demonstrating that dermoscopy facilitates identification of early vascular and subclinical nail involvement [18-20]. Patterns of nail involvement varied across patients, reflecting the heterogeneity of psoriasis. Clinically, distal onycholysis and pitting predominated, while dermoscopy highlighted vascular alterations, such as dilated capillaries and longitudinal erythema. Similar observations have been reported by Yorulmaz et al., who found pseudofibre sign, dilated capillaries, nail plate thickening and crumbling, subungual hyperkeratosis, transverse grooves, trachyonychia, pitting, and oil-dropping sign were correlated with NP severity [22]. Likewise, Arora et al.

demonstrated that higher PASİ scores correlated with increased NAPSİ, supporting the link between skin and nail disease burden [11]. Our results are consistent with these findings, with a significant correlation between PASİ and NAPSİ ($r = 0.371$, $p < 0.001$). Other studies further confirm dermoscopy’s superiority over clinical evaluation alone. Long et al. highlighted dermoscopic detection of onycholysis, splinter hemorrhages, pitting, longitudinal fissures, dilated streaky capillaries, and oil-dropping sign as key correlates of NP severity [17], while Asfiya et al. reported enhanced detection of subungual hyperkeratosis, transverse grooves, and trachyonychia on dermoscopy, reinforcing its sensitivity across disease stages and progression [19]. Further, the strong correlation between NAPSİ and DNAPSİ in our study ($r = 0.953$, $p < 0.001$) emphasizes the concordance between the two scoring systems’ ability to detect NP severity. Prior reports indicating that skin and nail disease severity, while often parallel, may also vary independently due to differing pathophysiologic and genetic influences [11]. Importantly, our studies indicated that the correlation between disease duration and NAPSİ was negligible ($r = 0.06$), suggesting that nail involvement does not necessarily worsen linearly with longer psoriasis history.

Conclusion

Taken together, our findings and prior literature establish dermoscopy as a simple and , practical tool for detecting subtle nail changes that may be missed by clinical observation alone. By

identifying early vascular and structural alterations, dermoscopy has the potential to guide earlier therapeutic intervention in psoriasis. Limitations of our study include monocentricity in its single-center design, relatively small sample size, and lack of inter-observer reliability assessment, which may limit the reproduction of findings. Future longitudinal studies with larger cohorts and multicenter participation may be needed to validate DNAPSI compared to NAPSI and explore its role in monitoring disease progression and treatment outcomes.

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